

SOCIAL AND BIOLOGICAL ADOLESCENT HEALTH PROBLEMS: THE WAY FORWARD

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Abstract

Adolescence is a unique phase of life and a significant period to lay the foundations of good health. The obvious being stated here is that most health challenges which individuals suffer in their adulthood are traceable to the lifestyles led during adolescence. This is because, during this stage of life, adolescents initiate patterns of behaviour which constitute health risks such as indulgence in smoking, alcohol and substance consumption, unprotected sex, unhealthy dieting, abortion, among others. This paper therefore made effort to expose the imperatives of adolescent health, considering its social and biological effects on the individual and the population. The paper adopted qualitative analysis approach based on relevant literatures. The paper concluded that healthy and well groomed adolescents will transit into healthy and responsible adults for the overall well-being of society, recommending that appropriate legislations and enforcement should be put in place to guard against risk-taking behaviours among adolescents such as alcohol and tobacco consumption, drug abuse and violence.